

1 **Abstract**

2 A series of Ni/hydroxyapatite samples presenting different Ca/P molar ratios were
3 synthesised to study the influence of the hydroxyapatite support composition on their
4 catalytic properties in the dry reforming of methane. Our results reveal that a
5 preparation starting from a sub-stoichiometric composition ($\text{Ca/P} < 1.67$) followed by
6 the impregnation of Ni results in suitable properties which give the highest catalytic
7 performance compared with stoichiometric ($\text{Ca/P} = 1.67$) and over-stoichiometric (Ca/P
8 $= 1.73$) compositions, respectively.

9 The characterisation of the investigated Ni/HAP materials shows that their texture,
10 surface chemistry (acid/base) and the Ni species distribution are mainly derived from
11 the structural properties of the used support. The activity of the Ni/HAP samples in
12 DRM shows that their performances follow this trend: Ni/HAP-D2 ($\text{Ca/P} = 1.62$) >
13 Ni/HAP-D1 (1.57) > Ni/HAP-S (1.67) > Ni/HAP-E (1.73). The superiority of the
14 sample with a Ca/P molar ratio of 1.62 was explained by a suitable surface chemistry
15 consisting of an abundance of strong acid sites and basic sites. While the former act as
16 anchoring sites for Ni species the latter serve as CO_2 chemisorption sites producing
17 intermediate species which in turn react with deposited carbon to form CO. This
18 distribution together with its improved textural properties lead to the deposition of
19 highly dispersed, efficient and coke resistant Ni species.

20

21

22 *Keywords: Hydroxyapatite, Ca/P molar ratio, Ni dispersion, acid/base properties,*
23 *methane dry reforming.*

24

1 **1. Introduction**

2 The choice of an appropriate technology for the production of synthesis gas (H_2 and
3 CO) from natural gas reforming is based on its end-use. In this sense, dry reforming of
4 methane (DRM) appears to be a suitable strategy for chemicals and fuel production
5 which require a H_2/CO ratio close to unity, as in the case of Fisher-Tropsch synthesis
6 [1-4]. Furthermore, its combination with other reforming processes, such as steam
7 reforming of methane (SRM), allows the adjustment of the resulting H_2/CO ratio when
8 specific values are needed [2,3]. Likewise, for environmental concerns, DRM is an
9 attractive strategy, fulfilling one of the constant challenges, because it allows the use of
10 greenhouse gases (CH_4 and CO_2) as reactants [1-4].

11 Nickel-based catalysts are widely used for DRM reaction owing to their activity and
12 competitive cost compared to noble metals [1-5]. Despite their high activity they suffer
13 from a rapid deactivation, due to carbon deposition, which is considered a major
14 drawback [1-10]. Hence, the catalysts for methane dry reforming should exhibit
15 adequate properties to endure the severe conditions of the reaction which is generally
16 carried out at high temperatures (> 600 °C). For this purpose, numerous catalytic
17 formulations were investigated in order to improve the sintering-resistance of the Ni
18 particles and to reduce the coke formation [1, 4-10]. The nature of the used support
19 seems to play a crucial role in controlling the distribution and then the stability of the Ni
20 active phases. In this sense, it would be essential to design Ni catalysts that exhibit
21 suitable metal-support interaction in order to provide highly dispersed and resistant
22 active phases. It is also well-known that the surface catalyst chemistry is a determinant
23 factor in orienting the process towards either the desirable products or undesirable side
24 reactions, such as methane cracking ($CH_4 \rightarrow C + 2H_2$) and Boudouard reaction ($2CO \rightarrow$
25 $C + CO_2$) [4-7]. However, a suitable distribution of acid and basic sites is still a matter

1 of controversy. For instance, it was reported that F addition to Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts
2 induces the formation of Lewis acidic species which stabilise the metallic Ni particles
3 from high-temperature sintering by enhancing metal-support interaction and reduces
4 coke deposition under DRM conditions [4]. By contrast, Bang et al. [5] linked the
5 excellent coke resistance and stability of Ni/P-Al₂O₃ catalysts in DRM reaction to their
6 weak acidity. Likewise, several studies reported that increasing the basic character of
7 the exposed surface minimises the possibility of carbon formation [3,6,9,10]. For
8 instance, Zhang et al. [6] found an improvement of the activity and stability of their
9 Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts by introducing small amounts of La as promoter. They attributed the
10 observed behaviour to the increased number of medium-strength basic sites.

11 Since the pioneer work by Boukha et al. [1] which demonstrated the promising
12 behaviour of hydroxyapatite (Ca₁₀(PO₄)₆(OH)₂ : HAP) supported Ni catalysts in the
13 DRM reaction, a number of studies dealing with the use of hydroxyapatite as a DRM
14 catalyst support have been available in the literature [11-17]. Commercial and/or
15 synthesised materials with a composition close to that of stoichiometric hydroxyapatite
16 (Ca/P = 1.67) are by far the most investigated for DRM application. These
17 investigations specially concern the effect of the nature of the active phase, metal
18 loading, promoter effect, preparation method and the experimental conditions of the
19 reaction, among others. However, no special attention has been devoted to the effect of
20 the stoichiometry of the HAP support on the catalytic performance of the supported
21 active phases in DRM. According to many reports, varying the Ca/P molar ratio leads to
22 the formation of additional phases and induces significant changes in the textural and
23 acid-base properties of the hydroxyapatite [18,19]. Silvester et al. [18] reported that as a
24 result of structural rearrangements Ca-deficient HAP (Ca/P < 1.67) tends to decompose
25 to stoichiometric HAP and Ca₃(PO₄)₂ whereas for a Ca/P ratio higher than 1.67 the

1 material should decompose to stoichiometric apatite and CaO. Tsuchida et al. [19] have
2 shown that the highly selective synthesis of 1-butanol and 1,3-butadiene from ethanol
3 could be merely controlled by the HAP catalyst's Ca/P molar ratio. They found that
4 product selectivity bore a strong correlation with the acid and basic properties tuned by
5 varying Ca/P ratio of the HAP catalysts.

6 The present study is dealing with the investigation on the influence of the Ca/P molar
7 ratio on the textural, structural, surface chemistry (acid/base) and catalytic behaviour in
8 DRM of a series of hydroxyapatite supported nickel samples (Ni/HAP). For this
9 purpose, hydroxyapatite supports with different Ca/P molar ratios have been
10 synthesised. Interesting conclusions will be presented by correlating the very rich
11 information provided by a wide battery of techniques (including BET, XRD, TEM,
12 FTIR, NH₃-TPD, CO₂-TPD and TPO) and the catalytic performance of the investigated
13 samples. To the best of our knowledge the influence of the composition, by varying the
14 Ca/P ratio, on the catalytic properties of Ni/HAP in DRM has not been yet investigated.

15

16 **2. Experimental**

17 Four HAP samples presenting different stoichiometry were synthesized by precipitation
18 method, adding drop wise a calcium nitrate solution (MERCK) to a solution of
19 (NH₄)₂HPO₄ (SIGMA-ALDRICH). In order to obtain different stoichiometries the pH
20 of the precipitation was adjusted, by adding ammonia solution, at 8.6, 9.3, 10 and 11.
21 The mixture was, then, stirred at 80 °C for 16 h. After filtration, the recovered solid was
22 washed with distilled water, dried overnight at 120 °C and finally calcined in air at
23 750 °C for 4 h. The prepared samples were named HAP-S, HAP-D1, HAP-D2 and
24 HAP-E based on the actual Ca/P molar ratio determined by ICP; where "S" refers to the

1 stoichiometric composition ($\text{Ca/P} = 1.67$), “D1” and “D2” to calcium-deficient samples
2 ($\text{Ca/P} < 1.67$) and “E” to calcium-enriched sample ($\text{Ca/P} > 1.67$).

3 Four Ni/HAP samples were prepared by incipient wetness impregnation of the
4 synthesised HAP supports, described above, from aqueous solutions containing equal
5 amount of Ni acetate tetrahydrate (SIGMA-ALDRICH, 98%) solution. The impregnated
6 samples were dried overnight at 120 °C and, then, calcined at 750 °C for 4 h (with a
7 ramp of 5 °C min⁻¹). The reduction of the prepared samples was carried out under
8 flowing 5% H_2 /Ar (60 cm³ min⁻¹) at 750 °C for 2 h with a ramp of 5 °C min⁻¹.

9 The N_2 physisorption experiments were performed on an automatic device
10 (Micromeritics, model TRISTAR II 3020). Prior analysis the samples were evacuated at
11 300 °C under nitrogen flow for 12 h.

12 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra for the prepared samples were
13 recorded with a Cary 600 Series FTIR apparatus using thin disks of samples (about 3
14 wt.%) diluted in KBr.

15 The structural properties of the bare supports and Ni-modified samples were
16 investigated by X-ray diffraction (XRD). The XRD experiments were conducted on a
17 X'PERT-MPD X-ray diffractometer with Cu $\text{K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) and a X-ray
18 tube operated at 40 kV and 40 mA. The samples were scanned between 10° and 100°
19 (2θ) at a scan rate of 0.13° s⁻¹. The weight fractions of crystalline phases in the as
20 calcined supports were determined using a Rietveld program by trial and error method.
21 This analysis concerned only the samples showing, besides the hydroxyapatite structure,
22 the presence of CaO as additional phase ($\text{Ca/P} \geq 1$). The full profile refinement of LaB_6
23 was used for the instrumental calibration. For the estimation of the average metallic Ni
24 particle size, by Scherrer equation, the samples were scanned between 43° and 46° with

1 a relatively slow rate ($0.0074^\circ \text{ s}^{-1}$) in order to improve the precision and the quality of
2 the most intense peak (111) at $44.7^\circ (\pm 0.1)$.

3 The morphology and the Ni particle size distributions, for the samples reduced at 750
4 $^\circ\text{C}$, were investigated by Transmission Electron microscopy (TEM). The corresponding
5 observations were performed using a JEOL 2010F microscope, working at 200 kV, with
6 a structural resolution of 0.19 nm. Likewise, high-angle annular dark-field scanning-
7 transmission (HAADF-STEM) technique was used for the observations of the spent
8 catalysts.

9 The Ni dispersion values were also estimated by H_2 chemisorption at 35°C using a
10 Micromeritics ASAP 2020 instrument. Prior to analysis, the samples were reduced in-
11 situ flowing $5\% \text{H}_2/\text{Ar}$ ($60 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$) at 750°C for 2 h. Thereafter, the samples were
12 purged under high vacuum at 750°C for 1 h and cooled to 35°C (during 3h). The H_2
13 adsorption measurements (at 35°C) consisted of an isotherm in the pressure range of 0-
14 200 torr. The Ni dispersion was estimated assuming a unity adsorption stoichiometry
15 ($\text{H}/\text{Ni}_s = 1$).

16 Temperature-programmed reduction (H_2 -TPR) experiments were conducted on a
17 Micromeritics AutoChem 2920 instrument equipped with a TCD detector and coupled
18 to a MKS Cirrus LM99 mass spectrometer. The samples were pre-treated in a flow of
19 $5\% \text{O}_2/\text{He}$ at 750°C for 30 min and then cooled down to 50°C under He flow.
20 Thereafter, the samples were reduced under a $5\% \text{H}_2/\text{Ar}$ flow ($50 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$) raising the
21 temperature from 50°C to 750°C with a ramp of $10^\circ \text{C min}^{-1}$.

22 Temperature-programmed oxidation (TPO) experiments were carried out in order to
23 determine the amounts and the nature of the coke deposited over the post-reaction
24 samples. The latter were heated up to 900°C at $10^\circ \text{C min}^{-1}$, in a $5\% \text{O}_2/\text{He}$ flow (60 cm^3

1 min⁻¹). The CO₂ signal (m/z = 44) was monitored online with a quadrupole mass
2 spectrometer (Pfeiffer, model Thermostar GSD301T1).

3 The temperature programmed desorption of CO₂ (CO₂-TPD) experiments were
4 conducted on a Micromeritics AutoChem 2920 instrument coupled to a mass
5 spectrometer (MKS Cirrus LM99). The pre-treatment of the samples consisted of their
6 reduction at 750 °C (2 h) in a flow 5%H₂/He and, then, their cooling to 50 °C in a flow
7 of He. The adsorption of CO₂ was carried out under a flow of 10%CO₂/He (50 cm³ min⁻¹)
8 for 30 min. Thereafter, the samples were treated with He (at 50 °C) for 2 h and
9 heated up to 900 °C with a ramp of 10 °C min⁻¹.

10 The acid properties of the samples were investigated by temperature programmed
11 desorption of NH₃ (NH₃-TPD). The samples were submitted to the same pre-treatment
12 used for CO₂-TPD. The adsorption of NH₃ was performed at 50 °C under a 10%NH₃/He
13 flow (50 cm³ min⁻¹) for 30 min. Then, they were treated with He for 2 h and heated up
14 to 750 °C (10 °C min⁻¹). The NH₃ signal (m/z = 15) was followed online by a MKS
15 Cirrus LM99 mass spectrometer.

16 The methane dry reforming experiments were performed in a quartz fixed-bed reactor
17 operating at atmospheric pressure. The catalysts (50 mg) gently mixed (using a spatula
18 in an agate mortar) with silicon carbide (100 mg) were pre-reduced under a 5%H₂/Ar
19 flow (60 cm³ min⁻¹) at 750 °C for 2 h; then, evacuated under flowing He (60 cm³ min⁻¹)
20 for 1 h. The reaction mixture was composed of 50%CH₄ and 50%CO₂ with a total flow
21 of 50 cm³ min⁻¹. The experiments were carried out at 750 °C for 24 h. The catalysts
22 were also tested, under more severe conditions, at relatively lower temperature (600 °C)
23 and more prolonged time on stream (65 h). The reactants (CH₄ and CO₂) and the
24 products (H₂ and CO) of the reaction were analysed by using a gas chromatograph
25 analyser (Bruker 450-GC). The CH₄ and CO₂ conversions were calculated as follows:

$$\text{CH}_4 \text{ conversion (\%)} = \frac{(\text{CH}_4)_{\text{in}} - (\text{CH}_4)_{\text{out}}}{(\text{CH}_4)_{\text{in}}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{CO}_2 \text{ conversion (\%)} = \frac{(\text{CO}_2)_{\text{in}} - (\text{CO}_2)_{\text{out}}}{(\text{CO}_2)_{\text{in}}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

1 The thermodynamic data were estimated by SimSci PRO II software by using the Gibbs
2 Energy Minimization Method.

3

4 **3. Results and discussion**

5 **3.1. Characterisation of the Ni/HAP samples**

6 **3.1.1. Textural characterisation studies**

7 The N₂ adsorption/desorption studies on the bare supports and Ni/HAP samples show
8 that their isotherms and hysteresis loops (H3) are similar (Fig. S1 and Fig. S2,
9 respectively). According to many authors, the observed isotherms are characteristics of
10 materials consisting of aggregated particles and/or exhibiting slit-shaped pores [20-21].
11 Fig. 1 displays the pore size distribution for all reduced samples. The traces for the
12 HAP-D1 and Ni/HAP-D1 samples show an asymmetric and wide distribution peaked at
13 53 nm. By increasing the Ca/P molar ratio from 1.57 to 1.62 the distribution becomes
14 narrower and the observed peak significantly shifts towards a lower value (33 nm). An
15 almost similar distribution could be observed for the stoichiometric samples (HAP-S
16 and Ni/HAP-S). The HAP-E support (Ca/P = 1.73) presents a relatively wider
17 distribution, but after addition of Ni (Ni/HAP-E), the resulting distribution appears to be
18 quite similar to that of the Ni/HAP-S and Ni/HAP-D2 samples.

19 Table 1 resumes the experimental data extracted from the analysis of the resulting
20 isotherms. The specific surface areas of Ca-deficient and stoichiometric supports (HAP-
21 D1, HAP-D2 and HAP-S) are found to be ranged between 25-31 m² g⁻¹. The Ca-
22 enriched support (HAP-E), however, shows the lowest S_{BET} value which does not

1 exceed $11 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$. A similar trend has been observed in previous studies [18,22], in
2 accordance with which, the observed loss could be associated to structural changes
3 induced by the excess of Ca species spread on the hydroxyapatite surface. With
4 reference to their respective bare supports, nickel deposition seems to induce a slight
5 decrease in the BET surface area of Ni/HAP-D1 (from 25 to $24 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$), Ni/HAP-D2
6 (from 31 to $26 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) and Ni/HAP-E (from 11 to $9 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$). By contrast, a significant
7 loss (by 32%) could be noticed in the case of the stoichiometric samples (from $25 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$
8 for HAP-S to $17 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for Ni/HAP-S).

9

10 **3.1.4. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)**

11 FTIR spectroscopy was used in order to evaluate the purity and structural properties of
12 the synthesised materials [23-29]. Fig. 2a and Fig. 2b display the FTIR spectra for the
13 HAP bare supports and Ni-modified HAP samples, calcined at $750 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively.

14 As observed in Fig. 2a the spectra of the bare supports show a set of five bands (peaked
15 at 570 , 602 , 962 , 1041 , 1092 and a shoulder near 1248 cm^{-1}), attributed to different
16 vibration modes of P-O bonds in the $(\text{PO}_4)^{3-}$ groups [23]. In addition, the presence of
17 structural hydroxyl groups in the hydroxyapatite result in characteristic bands centred at
18 637 and 3570 cm^{-1} [23,29].

19 In the 1400 - 1500 cm^{-1} region, the spectra present two bands, at 1415 and 1465 cm^{-1} ,
20 assigned to carbonates species. The presence of the high wavenumber band (1465 - 1470
21 cm^{-1}) indicates the incorporation of CO_3^{2-} ions, introduced from the atmosphere, into the
22 hydroxyapatite structure [18, 24, 25]. Hydroxyapatite structure can host carbonates in
23 two different sites by substitution of OH^- (A-type) and/or PO_4^{3-} (B-type) sites [18]. It is
24 worth mentioning that, in good agreement with a previous work [18], the intensity ratio
25 of this CO_3^{2-} band (1465 - 1470 cm^{-1}) to P-O bands (900 - 1250 cm^{-1}) linearly increases

1 with the Ca/P molar ratio increase (Fig. S3). Cheng et al. [24] claimed that the
2 occurrence of the structural carbonate band could be attributed to the CO_3^{2-} species that
3 occupy the PO_4^{3-} sites (B-type substitution). Their presence is unavoidable because
4 during the thermal treatment the hydroxyapatite is susceptible to contamination with
5 CO_3^{2-} ions coming from atmospheric CO_2 .

6 The spectra also exhibit two absorption bands, peaked at 1630 cm^{-1} and 3450 cm^{-1} , due
7 to water molecules. Interestingly, the spectrum of the Ca-enriched support (HAP-E)
8 reveals the occurrence of an absorption band, at 3645 cm^{-1} , belonging to the stretching
9 vibration of OH^- groups characteristic of calcium hydroxide species [25-27]. The
10 formation of the $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ species in Ca-rich hydroxyapatite is explained by a complex
11 process of structure reconstruction resulting from the substitution of tetrahedral PO_4^{3-} by
12 CO_3^{2-} ions [26,27]. Unexpectedly, this band is manifested as a shoulder in the case of
13 the stoichiometric support (HAP-S). The occurrence of the latter is a direct proof of the
14 deposition of Ca species which does not integrate the HAP structure. Moreover, with
15 reference to the stoichiometric support, the formation of this phase on the HAP-E
16 sample seems to affect the broad absorption due to the vibrations of adsorbed water
17 molecules (3450 cm^{-1}) which tends to split giving two maxima in the $3394\text{-}3485\text{ cm}^{-1}$
18 region. Similar behaviour was reported in our previous study on Co/hydroxyapatite
19 catalysts [23]. This was explained by a possible enrichment of the hydroxyapatite
20 surface by the metallic phase.

21 Addition of nickel to the stoichiometric (Ni/HAP-S) and Ca-deficient (Ni/HAP-D1 and
22 Ni/HAP-D2) samples seems to disturb significantly the vibrations of adsorbed water
23 molecules (Fig. 2b) suggesting an apparent enrichment of the supports surface by the
24 NiO phase. As expected, this effect is less important in the case of the Ca-enriched

1 sample (Ni/HAP-E). Yet, the occurrence of surface metallic phase, consisting of
2 $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, can only be unequivocally identified on its corresponding bare support.

3

4 **3.1.2. Reducibility of the Ni/HAP catalysts**

5 Fig. 3 displays the H_2 -TPR profiles for HAP and Ni/HAP samples, calcined at 750 °C.
6 The profiles of all bare supports are characterised by the presence of a reduction peak
7 centred at 450 °C with very low intensity. In line with our previous study [30] this peak
8 could be associated to a reversible redox process leading to a consumption of surface
9 oxygen anions species. The diagram of the Ni/HAP-D1 sample shows three reduction
10 peaks centred at 350 °C, 400 °C and 750 °C. The first one is assigned to the reduction of
11 surface NiO particles exhibiting weak interaction with the support (namely α). The
12 second peak could be attributed to the reduction of finely dispersed NiO particles in
13 strong interaction with the HAP-D1 support (namely β), whereas the third feature
14 (namely γ) is associated to the reduction of a fraction of Ni^{2+} which has incorporated the
15 HAP structure [1]. With reference to Ni/HAP-D1 the reduction profile of the Ni/HAP-
16 D2 catalyst shows that the position of the peaks attributed to the NiO species (α and β
17 species) shift slightly (by 20 °C) towards high temperatures; suggesting that the
18 interactions of these species with the HAP-D2 support are relatively stronger.
19 Interestingly, the position of the peak due to Ni^{2+} ion-exchanged species (γ) seems to be
20 almost constant on the two Ca-deficient samples. This result points out that the Ni^{2+}
21 ions incorporating the structure of both Ni/HAP-D1 and Ni/HAP-D2 samples occupy
22 cationic vacant sites of the same nature. The profiles of the Ni/HAP-S (Ca/P = 1.67) and
23 Ni/HAP-E (Ca/P > 1.67) samples, however, evidence the absence of the Ni^{2+} species,
24 integrating their respective supports structure. This suggests that the presence of CaO
25 species on these two catalysts makes the $\text{Ni}^{2+}/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ ion-exchange process more difficult,

1 even under a high calcination temperature. Similar observation was reported by Zhang
2 and Verykios [31] in their study on Ni/CaO/Al₂O₃ catalysts where they concluded that
3 the presence of CaO could retard the formation of the hardly reducible nickel aluminate
4 phase.

5 Table 2 lists quantitative data corresponding to H₂/Ni molar ratios, determined as mole
6 of H₂ per mole of total Ni, and the contribution of each Ni species, respectively. For all
7 Ni catalysts the calculated H₂/Ni values are slightly higher than that expected for the
8 reduction of stoichiometric NiO (1) revealing a possible contribution of the supports
9 reduction. Besides, the distribution of the Ni species between the three sites, previously
10 detected (α , β and γ species), seems to depend on the nature of the support. For
11 instance, the NiHAP-D2 sample exhibits the largest amount of NiO (β species) highly
12 interacting with the support (41.7%). By contrast, the Ni/HAP-S sample gives a major
13 contribution of α species (70.4%) suggesting that the reduction of NiO particles spread
14 over our stoichiometric HAP is somewhat easier with respect to the other samples.

15

16 **3.1.3. X-ray diffraction (XRD)**

17 The HAP and Ni/HAP samples, in their oxidised and reduced forms, were characterised
18 by X-ray powder diffraction techniques in order to investigate the effect of varying the
19 Ca/P molar ratio on their structural properties. Fig. 4a and Fig. 4b display the XRD
20 patterns for the HAP bare supports and their corresponding Ni-modified samples,
21 respectively. The diffractograms of the calcined HAP-D1, HAP-D2 samples (Fig. 4a)
22 evidence the formation of a unique crystalline phase, identical to that of hydroxyapatite
23 structure (P6_{3/m} space group) (JCPDS: 01-082-256). By contrast, the supports presenting
24 higher Ca/P molar ratio (HAP-S and HAP-E) give additional diffraction peak (37.6°)
25 assigned to the CaO phase (JCPDS: 00-02-0968). The contribution of the latter,

1 determined by the Rietveld refinement, is found to be about 2.7% for the HAP-S and
 2 5.6% for the HAP-E. It is worth noting that the fraction detected in the stoichiometric
 3 sample is accompanied by a too weak peak assigned to tricalcium phosphate phase
 4 (TCP) (JCPDS: 00-009-0348) which may be induced by the relatively high calcination
 5 temperature (750 °C). It is known that after a dehydroxylation process hydroxyapatite
 6 structure may decompose completely at elevated temperatures into TCP and CaO
 7 phases [32,33]. In this sense, Cihlar et al. [32] proposed the following scheme:

8 After reduction at 750 °C the HAP-S sample tends to exhibit structural properties
 9 similar to those of a stoichiometric hydroxyapatite. Especially, the intensity of the peak
 10 due to the CaO phase significantly decreases and the TCP feature disappears
 11 completely. This result would imply the reversibility of the decomposition process,
 12 described above.

13 As expected, the diffractograms of the calcined Ni/HAP-D1 and Ni/HAP-D2 show two
 14 peaks belonging to NiO phase (JCPDS: 89-7131) (Fig. 4b). The Ni/HAP-S and
 15 Ni/HAP-E samples, however, exhibit additional peaks due to CaO (overlaps a NiO
 16 signal) and β calcium pyrophosphate (β -CPP, β -Ca₂P₂O₇) (JCPDS: 09-0346). The
 17 occurrence of the β -CPP phase is explained by a structural arrangement, induced by the
 18 presence of NiO species, which concerns a local concentration of sites deficient in Ca²⁺
 19 ions. Thus, the distribution of Ca excess becomes divided between two phases
 20 consisting of CaO and β -CPP.

21 The patterns of all Ni/HAP post-reduction samples show that the NiO phase is
 22 completely reduced into metallic Ni (Ni⁰) (JCPDS: 89-7120). Moreover, the diagrams
 23 of the Ca-deficient samples (Ni/HAP-D1 and Ni/HAP-D2) reveal the appearance of the

1 TCP phase. It should be noted that, according to the H₂-TPR data, these samples have
2 shown the presence of hardly reducible phase consisting of ion-exchanged Ni²⁺ species.
3 It seems that the reduction process of the latter involves a partial transformation of the
4 HAP structure into TCP [30]. On the other hand, the measured crystallite sizes of the
5 hydroxyapatite phase in the reduced samples (Table 2) reveal a direct relationship with
6 their specific surface areas (Table 1). For instance, the samples with higher Ca/P ratios
7 (Ni/HAP-S and Ni/HAP-E) exhibit the largest crystallite sizes (44 and 51 nm,
8 respectively) whereas they bear the lowest S_{BET} values (17 and 9 m² g⁻¹).
9 Table 2 also lists the Ni⁰ particle size values calculated by Scherrer equation by using
10 the peak corresponding to (111) reticular plane. For this estimation the reduced samples
11 were scanned between 43° and 46° with a relatively slow rate (0.0074° s⁻¹) (Fig. S4). On
12 the Ca-deficient samples the average size of Ni⁰ particles is found to be ranged between
13 15.2 nm (Ni/HAP-D2) and 18 nm (Ni/HAP-D1). However, larger Ni⁰ particle sizes are
14 measured on the samples with higher Ca/P molar ratio (33.1 nm for Ni/HAP-S and 36
15 nm for Ni/HAP-E). It is clear that the structural and the resulting textural properties of
16 the used support play a key role in controlling the size of the deposited Ni⁰ particles.
17 The samples with Ca/P ≥ 1.67 suffer from a profound loss in their specific surface area
18 induced by their structure evolution (especially, the formation of the CaO phase).
19 Consequently, the surface density of the Ni species becomes significantly higher which,
20 in turn, could result in a deposition of larger Ni particles.

21

22 **3.1.4. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)**

23 The hydroxyapatite-supported nickel samples, reduced at 750 °C, were also investigated
24 by TEM techniques. Fig. 5 displays TEM images of the reduced Ni/HAP-D2 sample.
25 Likewise, Fig. S5 (a, b and c) and Fig. S6 present TEM micrographs corresponding to

1 Ni/HAP-D1, Ni/HAP-S and Ni/HAP-E catalysts and the particle size distribution traces
2 for all analysed samples, respectively. The samples do not show significant differences
3 in morphology (Fig. 5 and Fig. S5). In all cases spherical particles of metallic nickel are
4 observed. However, as shown in Fig. S6, the distribution of the Ni particle sizes seems
5 to depend on the used support. The Ca-deficient samples (Ni/HAP-D1 and Ni/HAP-D2)
6 present almost similar shape consisting of a relatively narrow distribution peaked
7 around 11-15 nm. Over the stoichiometric sample (Ni/HAP-S) the sizes of the detected
8 Ni population shift towards higher values presenting a peak at 17-19 nm. By contrast,
9 the distribution over the Ca-enriched sample (Ni/HAP-E) is significantly much broader
10 (ranged between 15 and 55 nm) and appears to be heterogeneous compared to the other
11 samples. Table 2 lists the average size and the dispersion of Ni particles. The Ni/HAP-
12 D2 exhibits the smallest size (17 nm) followed by Ni/HAP-D1 (18.5 nm). Moreover,
13 increasing the Ca/P ratio to reach values close to 1.67 (Ni/HAP-S) and 1.73 (Ni/HAP-E)
14 would imply a significant increase in the size of Ni particles (22 and 34.3 nm,
15 respectively). It is worth outlining that, though they differ slightly from each other, the
16 general trend of these observed values is fully consistent with the XRD results,
17 discussed above.

18

19 **3.1.5. H₂ chemisorption study**

20 Table 2 also reports the Ni dispersion and the Ni particle size for all reduced catalysts as
21 determined by H₂ chemisorption. The objective of these experiments is to determine
22 quantitatively the capacity of the surface Ni active phases to chemisorb H₂ molecule. As
23 can be deduced from Table 2, the general trend of Ni particle size values matches very
24 well with those estimated by TEM and XRD techniques. However, the dispersion data
25 indicate that the values determined by H₂ chemisorption are in all cases lower than those

1 given by XRD and TEM. This suggests that a fraction of the deposited Ni particles is
2 not accessible to the gas phase. For this reason, in the following, the reactivity of the
3 sites associated to Ni species will be correlated to the metallic surface area estimated by
4 H₂ chemisorption.

5

6 **3.1.6. Acid-base properties of the Ni/HAP catalysts**

7 **3.1.6.1. Temperature programmed desorption of NH₃ (NH₃-TPD)**

8 The thermal stability of pre-adsorbed NH₃ on the acid sites of the reduced HAP and
9 Ni/HAP catalysts was studied by means of NH₃-TPD techniques (Fig. 6). Table 3 and
10 Table S2 summarise the total amounts and the distribution of the acid sites, respectively,
11 calculated by integration of their respective desorption peaks. Data corresponding to the
12 bare supports are also included in order to be used as reference.

13 As shown in Fig. 6, the traces of all analysed supports consist of two desorption
14 domains, suggesting the presence of at least two adsorption sites with different natures.
15 The first peak centred around 300-320 °C is ascribed to medium-strength acid sites on
16 the surface of the solids whereas the second feature (T > 600 °C) could be assigned to
17 strong acid sites. The latter was also reported by Lonyi et al. [34] in their study on the
18 adsorption of ammonia over zeolite materials. They attributed its occurrence to a
19 desorption of NH₃ from strong Lewis acid sites.

20 Interestingly, the Ca-deficient samples (HAP-D1 and HAP-D2) show similar surface
21 density of acid sites (0.53-0.54 μmol m⁻²) (Table 3) and exhibit almost identical
22 distribution, being composed of 66-68% of medium-strength acid sites (0.35-0.37 μmol
23 m⁻²) and 32-34% of strong acid sites (0.17-0.18 μmol m⁻²) (Table S2). Furthermore, the
24 effect of increasing the Ca/P molar ratio from 1.62 (HAP-D2) to 1.67 (HAP-S) would
25 mainly consist of an increase in the medium-strength acid sites fraction (from 66% to

1 80%, respectively) at the expense of the strong acid sites (from 34% to 20%,
2 respectively). As expected, a significant decrease in the overall density of adsorption
3 sites is observed for the Ca-enriched sample (HAP-E) which does not exceed $0.46 \mu\text{mol}$
4 m^{-2} . Silvester et al. [18] attributed the acidic properties of hydroxyapatites to surface
5 HPO_4^{2-} and OH^- vacancies mainly occurring on Ca-deficient samples, denoted as Ca_{10-}
6 $z(\text{HPO}_4)_z(\text{PO}_4)_{6-z}(\text{OH})_{2-z}$ ($0 < z \leq 1$) [23]. Moreover, they linked the observed decrease
7 in the number of acid sites with the Ca/P increase to the formation of CaO species on
8 the hydroxyapatite surface. Nevertheless, when compared to the others supports, the
9 HAP-E sample exhibits relatively the highest density of strong sites ($0.22 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}$)
10 which represent 48% of the acid sites (Table S2).

11 The impregnation of nickel onto the studied supports influences significantly the
12 amounts and the distribution of the acid sites (Fig. 6, Table 3 and Table S2). For
13 instance, after deposition of nickel onto HAP-D1 support the peak due to medium-
14 strength acid sites tends to split into two peaks, having maxima at $275 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $380 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$,
15 which implies the occurrence of new weak adsorption sites. Similar observation could
16 be noticed in the case of the other Ni modified samples. However, the position of the
17 two resulting peaks seems to depend on the Ca/P molar ratio. The low temperature
18 peak, for example, shifts from $275 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for the Ni/HAP-D1 to $260 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for Ni/HAP-D2, to
19 $220 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for Ni/HAP-S and to $192 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for Ni/HAP-E.

20 On the other hand, as can be deduced from Table 3, among all investigated samples the
21 Ni/HAP-D1 bears the largest amounts and the highest surface density of acid sites (17.6
22 $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{NH}_3} \text{g}^{-1}$ and $0.73 \mu\text{mol}_{\text{NH}_3} \text{m}^{-2}$, respectively). Moreover, depending on the nature of
23 the support, the effect of Ni addition on the amounts and the distribution of acid sites
24 seem to proceed via different pathways (Table S2). This would mainly consist of an
25 increase in the surface density of acid sites for Ni/HAP-D1 (from 0.54 to $0.73 \mu\text{mol}_{\text{NH}_3}$

1 m^{-2}) and Ni/HAP-E (from 0.46 to 0.69 $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{NH}_3} \text{m}^{-2}$). By contrast, the values
2 corresponding to Ni/HAP-D2 (0.53 $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{NH}_3} \text{m}^{-2}$) and Ni/HAP-S (0.62 $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{NH}_3} \text{m}^{-2}$)
3 reveal that the impregnation of Ni does not affect the surface acid sites density
4 measured on their supports (HAP-D2 and Ni/HAP-S, respectively). It is worth
5 mentioning that, irrespective of the Ni-modified sample an increase in the density of
6 strong acid sites could be observed (compared with their bare supports) which becomes
7 almost constant (0.24-0.26 $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{NH}_3} \text{m}^{-2}$). This implies that these strong sites are
8 associated with the effective predominance of surface Ni species. In other words, we
9 claim that these strong acid sites might act as anchoring sites for stabilising Ni metals,
10 as reported in previous work [4]. In this sense, a linear relationship between the metallic
11 surface area, determined by H_2 chemisorption, and the number of strong acid sites could
12 be observed (Fig. S7).

13

14 **3.1.6.2. Temperature programmed desorption of CO_2 (CO_2 -TPD)**

15 The surface basicity of the reduced HAP and Ni/HAP samples has been characterised
16 by means of CO_2 -TPD techniques. Fig. 7 displays the corresponding desorption profiles
17 after adsorption of CO_2 at 50 °C. Four desorption regions associated with different
18 strengths can be observed on the CO_2 -TPD diagrams (Fig. 7). The samples show
19 desorption peaks, located at low temperatures (< 300 °C), and ascribed to weak basic
20 sites. However, the peaks associated with medium-strength basic sites, occurring in the
21 second temperature range (300-550 °C), can only be observed for stoichiometric (HAP-
22 S and Ni/HAP-S) and Ca-enriched (HAP-E and Ni/HAP-E) samples. Thus, the
23 occurrence of such sites could be due to the formation of CaO species on the
24 hydroxyapatite surface [18]. This is in good agreement with our FTIR and XRD data,

1 discussed before, where a contribution of CaO phase inherent to the excess Ca has been
2 detected in the reduced HAP-E and HAP-S samples.

3 At high temperatures ($T > 550$ °C), irrespective of the examined sample, the CO₂
4 desorption process gives two well resolved peaks. The first one (550-800 °C) is
5 probably due to strong surface basic. According to previous reports these sites are
6 principally consisting of surface OH⁻ species which strongly interact with CO₂
7 molecules [18,30]. The second feature ($T > 800$ °C) could be ascribed to the
8 decomposition of structural carbonate rather than to surface species. In order to evaluate
9 this hypothesis a blank TPD experiment was carried out on the HAP-E bare support
10 (Fig. S8). In this case the sample was submitted to the same pre-treatment applied for
11 the CO₂-TPD experiment (reduction at 750 °C for 2 h), but it was not exposed to CO₂
12 adsorption. As expected, the corresponding TPD diagram shows that no desorption peak
13 could be observed at temperatures lower than 800 °C. However, it evidences the
14 desorption of significant amounts of CO₂, retained probably in the hydroxyapatite
15 structure, at high temperatures (> 800 °C). As stated previously, these carbonate species
16 are located in the hydroxyapatite framework by substitution of PO₄³⁻ ions.

17 Table 3 reports the amounts and the distribution of CO₂ desorption sites, classified
18 according to their strength/nature, determined by integration of the peaks centred in the
19 four temperature regions (50-300 °C, 300-550 °C, 550-800 °C and > 800 °C). For
20 comparison, data corresponding to the bare supports are also included. As expected, the
21 overall density of desorption sites increases with the Ca/P molar ratio increase (2.3
22 $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$, for Ni/HAP-D1, 2.9 $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$, for Ni/HAP-D2, 4.6 $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$, for
23 Ni/HAP-S, and 11.2 $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$, for Ni/HAP-E). Likewise, in line with previous
24 findings [18,19], the density of the medium-strength basic sites, strong basic sites and
25 structural carbonate increase systematically as the Ca/P molar ratio is increased. This

1 tendency is explained by a structural evolution where the hydroxyapatite surface is
2 progressively enriched by CaO, OH⁻ and structural carbonate, respectively. In order to
3 separate the concept of this distribution, in the following, the basic sites occurring on
4 the HAP phase surface will be called HAP basic sites whereas those related to the CaO
5 phase will be named CaO basic sites.

6

7 **3.2. Catalytic activity in DRM**

8 The in-situ reduced Ni/HAP catalysts were assayed in the DRM reaction at 750 °C for
9 24 h. Fig. 8 (a, b and c) shows CH₄ and CO₂ conversions and the resulting H₂/CO molar
10 ratio, respectively. Table 4 reports the catalytic activity data at 24 h and the coke
11 deposition amounts (wt.%), estimated by TPO. In addition, in order to be used as
12 reference Ni catalysts data, extracted from the literature, are also reported.

13 As shown in Fig. 8a the Ni/HAP-D2 sample exhibits the highest initial conversion of
14 methane (80%) followed by NiHAP-D1 (78%). These values are significantly lowered,
15 with the increase in the Ca/P ratio, which become ranged between 72 and 73% over the
16 Ni/HAP-E and Ni/HAP-S, respectively. A similar trend can be observed when the
17 comparison is made on the basis of their initial CO₂ conversion values. Irrespective of
18 the tested catalyst the latter gives values (82-89%) higher than those of CH₄ conversion
19 (Fig. 8b). Moreover, the resulting initial H₂/CO values registered over all catalysts are
20 lower than 1 (0.77-0.80) (Fig. 8c). This could be explained by the occurrence of the
21 reverse water-gas shift reaction, where a fraction of produced H₂ reacts with CO₂
22 producing carbon monoxide and water [35-46]. On the basis of their performances the
23 assayed catalysts follow this general trend: Ni/HAP-D2 > Ni/HAP-D1 > Ni/HAP-S >
24 Ni/HAP-E. Then, it is clear that the activity is improved over the catalysts presenting a
25 deficiency in calcium. Furthermore, except for NiHAP-E, the catalysts demonstrate a

1 very good stability, in the studied time on stream. For instance, the Ni/HAP-D2 sample
2 exhibits only 2.5% activity loss after 24 h reaction (from 80 to 78%). However, the Ca-
3 enriched sample (Ni/HAP-E) suffers from deactivation to a larger extent (5.5%); over
4 which methane conversion decreases from 72 to 68%. On the other hand, the TPO
5 results for the post-reaction catalysts show a good resistance against coke deposition
6 which, in all cases, does not reach 1% (Table 4). This is actually expected considering
7 the relatively high temperature of the reaction (750 °C) [31,36,37]. In parallel, HAADF-
8 STEM analysis of the used samples show that there is no significant changes in the Ni
9 particle size when compared with the freshly reduced samples. Moreover, images of
10 Ni/HAP-D2 (Fig. S9), Ni/HAP-S (Fig. S10) and Ni/HAP-E (Fig. S11) spent catalysts
11 show that the deposited carbon is mainly filament-shaped which explain the high
12 resistance of the catalysts to deactivation. Nevertheless, as can be observed in Fig. 9
13 (corresponding to Ni/HAP-E spent sample) some analysed zones evidence the presence
14 of other forms of carbonaceous species which encapsulate Ni particles. According to
15 many reports, the deposition of filamentous carbon penalises at much lesser extent the
16 activity of the Ni catalysts in DRM compared to those encapsulating the active species
17 [13,38].

18 Fig. S12a and Fig. S12b displays the XRD patterns and the TPO diagrams, respectively,
19 recorded over the spent catalysts. In contrast to their freshly reduced counterpart, the
20 diffractograms of the tested Ni/HAP-S and NiHAP-E samples evidence the absence of
21 the CaO phase. In parallel, the peak attributed to the β -CPP phase becomes significantly
22 more intense (Fig. S12a) when compared to that exhibited by the reduced samples (Fig.
23 4). There is a second difference worth of outlining. The used Ca-enriched sample
24 (Ni/HAP-E) presents additional intense peak due to the formation of a graphitic carbon
25 phase (Fig. S12a). This result is consistent with the relatively highest conversion loss

1 (5.5%) observed for this sample and the encapsulation of Ni particles by carbonaceous
2 species detected by HAADF. Nevertheless, the observed deactivation mainly occurs
3 during the first hour of TOS after what the catalyst appear to be more stable (Fig. 8).
4 This behaviour is typical for carbon diffusion in the Ni lattice which proceeds until its
5 saturation [39,46].

6 As can be deduced from Table 4 methane and CO₂ conversions achieved by the
7 Ni/HAP-D2 (78% and 86%, respectively) after 24 h reaction are close to those
8 corresponding to the thermodynamic equilibrium (83.7% and 90.3%, respectively).
9 These results clearly outperform those shown by Ni/alumina and Ni/CZ catalysts,
10 reported in previous works [5,35]. Likewise, it is worth outlining the superiority of our
11 investigated home-made and free-promoter materials compared to a Ni-Co catalyst
12 supported on a commercial hydroxyapatite support [13]. Even though, the latter was
13 tested under less severe conditions (Table 4).

14 Fig. 10a and Fig. 10b display the dependence of the catalytic activity, after 24 h
15 reaction, on the metallic surface area (measured by H₂ chemisorption) and the number
16 of strong acid sites, respectively. The reported data reveal a linear increase in methane
17 and CO₂ conversion, respectively, and H₂/CO ratio with increasing the specific Ni
18 surface area and the number of strong acid sites, respectively. As discussed before, the
19 distribution of Ni on the catalyst surface is linked to the effective abundance of the
20 strong acid sites. This feature is markedly gathered on the Ca-deficient samples. It
21 seems that anchoring active metallic phase on these sites induces a strong metal-support
22 interaction and, then, a positive effect on the observed activity and stability of the
23 catalysts. In a previous study [4] on the behaviour of F-modified Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts in
24 DRM, it was found that their activity and stability were associated to the presence of

1 strong Lewis acid sites which stabilised the Ni particles from sintering through an
2 enhanced metal-support interaction.

3 It is also worth analysing the effect of the basic sites on the activity of the investigated
4 catalysts. Fig. 10c shows a relationship between the activity and the number of surface
5 HAP basic sites. It seems that the abundance of the latter appears to be beneficial for the
6 Ni/HAP activity in DRM. In this sense, it is well-known that surface basicity leads to
7 increased adsorption of CO₂ producing intermediate species which in turn react with
8 deposited carbon to form CO [39-41]. However, no clear effect, neither positive nor
9 negative, could be associated to the CaO species, detected on the freshly reduced
10 stoichiometric (Ni/HAP-S) and the Ca-enriched (Ni/HAP-E) samples. As revealed by
11 CO₂-TPD these species induce specially the formation of surface medium-strength basic
12 centres. We claim that their presence, at least under our experimental conditions, does
13 not affect the catalytic properties of the tested catalysts. Our conclusion is in line with
14 previous studies which claimed that, despite providing an advantageous basic character,
15 modification of Ni catalysts by CaO does not significantly influence their activity in
16 DRM [39,42].

17 In order to examine the effect of Ca/P on the capacity of the catalysts to endure more
18 severe conditions, inducing an increase in the coke formation [31,36,37], additional
19 experiments have been carried out at relatively low temperature (600 °C) and more
20 prolonged time on stream (65 h). For this study the catalysts exhibiting the lowest and
21 the highest Ca/P ratio (1.57 and 1.73, respectively) have been assayed (Fig. 11). As
22 expected, the two catalysts exhibit lower initial CH₄ and CO₂ conversions compared to
23 their respective values shown at 750 °C. The initial methane conversion becomes about
24 59% over Ni/HAP-D1 whereas 40% is shown over Ni/HAP-E. Likewise, the Ni/HAP-
25 D1 maintains its superiority in terms of its initial CO₂ conversion (47% vs. 33% over

1 Ni/HAP-E). Nevertheless, the two catalysts seem to suffer from a deactivation process
2 in similar way. Over Ni/HAP-D1 catalyst the methane conversion decreases quickly
3 during the first seven hours from 59% to 48%. Thereafter, the deactivation rate appears
4 to be lower where the catalyst gives a CH₄ conversion close to 42% at 65 h. Table S3
5 resumes the obtained results on the two tested catalysts. As stated before, the extent of
6 deactivation occurring on the two samples is almost the same. After 65 h reaction their
7 activity decreases by 28.2±0.5 %. The TPO analyses performed on the two spent
8 catalysts show that their resistance against coke formation are very similar (coke
9 formation around 7-8%) (Table S3) and the shapes of their TPO traces (Fig. S13)
10 consist mainly of a CO₂ formation peak centred at 610±10 °C. Moreover, XRD analyses
11 evidence the formation of graphitic carbon on the two tested samples. This suggests that
12 carbonaceous species exhibiting the same nature are deposited on the two catalysts.
13 These results confirm that the activity of the tested catalysts might be associated to the
14 abundance of the same active sites which suffer from a similar deactivation process.

15

16 **4. Conclusions**

17 The present study sheds light on the crucial role that plays the composition of the
18 hydroxyapatite materials when used as support for metallic Ni nanoparticles in their
19 catalytic properties in the DRM reaction. It seems that a preparation starting from a sub-
20 stoichiometric composition (Ca/P < 1.67) results in suitable properties which give the
21 highest catalytic performance compared with stoichiometric (Ca/P = 1.67) and over-
22 stoichiometric (Ca/P = 1.73) compositions, respectively.

23 We assume that the texture, the surface chemistry and the Ni species distribution shown
24 by the investigated materials are mainly derived from the structural properties of the
25 support used. Indeed, the XRD data showed that after their calcinations at 750 °C the

1 Ca-deficient samples contain NiO, Ni²⁺ ion-exchanged species and HAP phases; while
2 their reduction induces the deposition of metallic Ni and a fraction of TCP phase
3 together with the HAP structure. However, in the stoichiometric and Ca-enriched
4 samples, in addition to Ni⁰ and HAP structures, a considerable contribution of the CaO
5 phase inherent to the excess Ca has been detected. These structural differences seem to
6 have an impact on their textural properties. Upon increasing the Ca/P ratio the samples
7 suffer from a significant decrease in the specific surface area (from 26 to 9 m² g⁻¹) and
8 pore diameter (from 44 to 32 nm). In parallel, this is accompanied by a loss in the
9 number of both strong acid sites and basic sites lying on the hydroxyapatite surface.
10 However, the stoichiometric and Ca-enriched samples bear, besides the HAP basic sites,
11 medium-strength basic centres due to surface CaO species. In turn, these textural and
12 surface chemistry evolutions result in a decrease in the dispersion of the Ni particles
13 spreading on the surface of the reduced catalysts. Especially, it was found a relationship
14 between the abundance of surface strong acid sites, which might act as anchoring sites
15 for stabilising Ni metals, and the improved dispersion of Ni particles.

16 The catalytic activity of the Ni/HAP samples in DRM at 750 °C shows that their
17 performances follow this trend: Ni/HAP-D2 (Ca/P = 1.62) > Ni/HAP-D1 (1.57) >
18 Ni/HAP-S (1.67) > Ni/HAP-E (1.73). The superiority of the sample with a Ca/P molar
19 ratio of 1.62 was explained by its improved textural properties (26 m² g⁻¹) and a suitable
20 surface chemistry consisting of an abundance of strong acid sites and basic sites. While
21 the former act as anchoring sites for Ni species the latter serve as CO₂ chemisorption
22 sites which, in turn, react with deposited carbon to form CO. This distribution together
23 with its improved textural properties lead to the deposition of highly dispersed, efficient
24 and coke resistant Ni species.

25

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20 **CAPTIONS FOR TABLES AND FIGURES**

Table 1	Elemental analyses and textural properties data for the prepared catalysts
Table 2	H ₂ -TPR, XRD, TEM and H ₂ chemisorption data for the Ni/HAP catalysts
Table 3	Acid and base properties of the HAP and Ni/HAP samples as determined by NH ₃ -TPD and CO ₂ -TPD, respectively
Table 4	DRM catalytic performance (at 750 °C) of the Ni/HAP catalysts. Comparison with Ni catalysts reported in the literature.
Figure 1	Pore size distribution for the reduced HAP bare supports and Ni/HAP catalysts

- Figure 2 FTIR spectra for the calcined (a) HAP supports and (b) Ni/HAP catalysts
- Figure 3 H₂-TPR diagrams for the HAP and Ni/HAP samples.
- Figure 4 XRD patterns for the (a) HAP supports and (b) Ni/HAP catalysts: (c) samples calcined at 750 °C and (r) samples reduced at 750 °C.
- Figure 5 TEM micrograph for the reduced Ni/HAP-D2 catalyst.
- Figure 6 NH₃-TPD profiles for the reduced HAP bare supports and Ni/HAP catalysts
- Figure 7 CO₂-TPD profiles for the reduced HAP bare supports and Ni/HAP catalysts.
- Figure 8 DRM activity over Ni/HAP catalysts at 750 °C: (a) CH₄ conversion, (b) CO₂ conversion and (c) H₂/CO ratio.
- Figure 9 HAADF-STEM images of the Ni/HAP-E spent catalyst (DRM at 750 °C) evidencing the encapsulation of Ni particles. Images (d), (e) and (f) display the colour maps for Ni (red) and C (green).
- Figure 10 Dependence of DRM activity on (a) metallic surface area, (b) number of strong acid sites and (c) number of basic sites excluding those due to the CaO phase.
- Figure 11 DRM activity over Ni/HAP-D1 and Ni/HAP-E catalysts at 600 °C: (a) CH₄ conversion, (b) CO₂ conversion and (c) H₂/CO ratio.

Sample	pH ^(a) (± 0.1)	ICP ^(b)		BET ^(c)		
		Ca/P (± 0.01)	Ni, wt.% (± 0.03)	S _{BET} , m ² g ⁻¹	V _p , cm ³ g ⁻¹	d _p , nm
HAP-D1	8.6	1.57	0	25	0.28	49
HAP-D2	9.3	1.62	0	31	0.29	32
HAP-S	10	1.67	0	25	0.22	32
HAP-E	11	1.73	0	11	0.10	29
Ni/HAP-D1	-	1.57	3.41	24	0.28	44
Ni/HAP-D2	-	1.62	3.41	26	0.25	36
Ni/HAP-S	-	1.67	3.41	17	0.16	32
Ni/HAP-E	-	1.73	3.41	9	0.08	32

(a) pH of precipitation during the supports synthesis.

(b) Elemental analysis.

(c) Data corresponding to the samples reduced at 750 °C

Table 1

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Sample	H ₂ -TPR			XRD		TEM		H ₂ chemisorption			
	H ₂ /Ni	α, %	β, %	γ, %	HAP, nm	Ni°, nm	Disp, %	Ni°, nm	Disp, %		
Ni/HAP-D1	1.06	63.4	28.2	8.3	41 (40)	18	6.9	18.5	6.7	22.5	5.5
Ni/HAP-D2	1.04	49.4	41.7	8.9	34 (29)	15.2	8.2	17	7.3	18.3	6.8
Ni/HAP-S	1.05	70.4	29.6	0	44 (48)	33.1	3.8	22	5.7	35.5	3.5
Ni/HAP-E	1.03	61.7	38.3	0	51 (49)	36	3.5	34.3	3.6	42.8	2.9

5 Data in brackets correspond to the bare supports.

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Table 2

NH₃-TPDCO₂-TPD

Sample	Total amount of acid sites, $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{NH}_3} \text{g}^{-1}$		Surface density of acid sites, $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{NH}_3} \text{m}^{-2}$		Total amount of desorbed CO_2 , $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{g}^{-1}$	Surface density of CO_2 desorption sites, $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$		Distribution of CO_2 desorption sites, $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$			
	$\mu\text{mol}_{\text{NH}_3} \text{g}^{-1}$	$\mu\text{mol}_{\text{NH}_3} \text{m}^{-2}$	$\mu\text{mol}_{\text{NH}_3} \text{g}^{-1}$	$\mu\text{mol}_{\text{NH}_3} \text{m}^{-2}$		$\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$	$\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$	Weak basic sites ^(a)	Medium-strength basic sites ^(b)	Strong basic sites ^(c)	Structural carbonate ^(d)
HAP-D1	13.4	0.54	44.5	1.8	0.59	0	0.57	0.62			
HAP-D2	16.5	0.53	92	3.0	0.78	0	1.14	1.04			
HAP-S	15	0.60	102.4	4.1	0.67	0.28	1.71	1.43			
HAP-E	5.1	0.46	97	8.8	1.15	1.42	2.94	3.31			
Ni/HAP-D1	17.6	0.73	54.6	2.3	1.20	0	0.47	0.58			
Ni/HAP-D2	13.7	0.53	75	2.9	1.15	0	0.86	0.86			
Ni/HAP-S	10.6	0.62	78.6	4.6	0.92	0.68	1.41	1.61			
Ni/HAP-E	6.2	0.69	100.8	11.2	1.12	2.87	2.53	4.69			

1 (a) Determined by integration of the CO_2 -TPD peak centred at $T \leq 300$ °C.

2 (b) Determined by integration of the CO_2 -TPD peak at 300 °C $\leq T \leq 550$ °C.

3 (c) Determined by integration of the CO_2 -TPD peak at 550 °C $\leq T \leq 800$ °C.

4 (d) Determined by integration of the CO_2 -TPD peak centred at $T > 800$ °C.

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Table 3

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Catalyst	$X_{\text{CH}_4}^{(a)}$	$X_{\text{CO}_2}^{(a)}$	H_2/CO	Reaction mixture $\text{CH}_4/\text{CO}_2/\text{N}_2$	$\text{GHSV, cm}^3 \text{ h}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1}$	TOS, h	Coke, %	Reference
Ni/HAP-D1	75	83	0.78	50/50/0	60,000	24	0.6	
Ni/HAP-D2	78	86	0.79	50/50/0	60,000	24	0.8	This work
Ni/HAP-S	70	80	0.75	50/50/0	60,000	24	0.7	
Ni/HAP-E	67	78	0.72	50/50/0	60,000	24	0.9	
Ni/P-Al ₂ O ₃	63	61	0.86	40/40/20	60,000	20	8	[5]
Ni/CYSZ	66	78	0.70	50/50/0	60,000	24	7	[34]
Ni-Co/HAP	73	79	n.d.	20/20/60	15,882	24	n.d.	[13]
Ni-Mg-Al-La	65	75	n.d.	50/50/0	24,000	10	n.d.	[42]
NiCo/CeZrO ₂	78	84	0.84	50/50/0	12,000	80	0.3	[43]
Ni-Co/SiC-CeZr	74	80	0.75	50/50/0	12,000	23	0.5	[44]

(a) The margin of error is around 1%.

Table 4

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

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Figure 3

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Figure 4

Figure 5

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Figure 7

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Figure 8

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Figure 9

Figure 10

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Figure 11